

Adsorbents prepared by pyrolysis for VOC abatement

Zuzana Jankovská

zuzana.jankovska@vsb.cz

Institute of Environmental Technology, CEET, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6079-1658>

Pavλίna Peikertová

Nanotechnology Centre, CEET, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6272-2744>

Jonáš Tokarský

Department of Thermal Engineering, FMST, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava

Lenka Matějová

Institute of Environmental Technology, CEET, VSB–Technical University of Ostrava

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8816-0070>

Research Article

Keywords: waste animal bones, pyrolysis, VOC, adsorption, calcium

Posted Date: October 10th, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7807256/v1>

License: This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

[Read Full License](#)

Additional Declarations: The authors declare no competing interests.

Abstract

This study examines the production of char from waste animal bones via pyrolysis, and assesses their chemical and structural properties in relation to their capacity for absorbing volatile organic compounds (VOC). The type of raw input material has a greater impact on the yield of pyrolysis than the process conditions of the pyrolysis process. VOC adsorption capacity is influenced by porous structure, solid carbon content and the presence of calcium.

1. Introduction

Meat processing plants produce approximately 130 billion kg of animal bone waste annually[1]. This and other slaughterhouse waste are either landfilled or disposed of in rendering plants according to EU legislation on safety regulations. The fees charged by commercial rendering plants for the disposal of animal waste represent additional costs for meat production.

One of the used methods for processing animal by-products is pyrolysis, which involves thermochemical conversion in an oxygen-free atmosphere to gaseous, liquid, and solid products. The resulting solid phase (char), is a material with favourable textural properties, high surface functionality, and cation exchange capacity, which is effective for adsorption [2].

Char has been also studied for the adsorption of organic molecules [2–4], for removal of fluorides [5–8], sulphur [9], arsenic [7] or cations [10, 11]. Using char for adsorption could be an effective and safe way to dispose of this waste [10].

To our knowledge, only one study [12], deals with VOCs adsorption on char has been published beyond our research team. The removal of VOCs from the environment is not a negligible issue.

According to above, this article aims to the production of char using pyrolysis of waste bones from three animal species. The chemical, textural, and structural properties of char were studied, and the adsorption of VOC was thoroughly investigated in order to describe the factors determining adsorption capacity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Input material

Waste animal bones-input material was provided by company Těšínské jatky, s.r.o. (Czech Republic) and DIEMA s.r.o. (Czech Republic).

2.2. Sample preparation and VOC adsorption measurement

The pyrolysis and VOC adsorption apparatuses used in this study is described in detail in our previous studies [13, 14].

2.3. Characterisation techniques

The amounts of proteins, dry matter, fat, sugar, fibre, and starch were determined at Ekocentrum Ovalab (Czech Republic). Proximate and ultimate analysis were performed using LECO CHNS 628, LECO AC 350. Thermogravimetric curves were measured using SDT 600. Physical nitrogen adsorption was performed at 77 K on a 3Flex. Raman spectra were obtained using an XploRA™. FTIR spectra were recorded using Nicolet 6700 FT-IR. Chemical composition was determined using XEPOS. Phase composition and microstructural properties were determined using Rigaku SmartLab. Morphology and surface changes were studied using Tescan Vega. Molecular modeling was performed using Materials Studio 4.2. XPS measurements were performed using the Nexsa G2.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of input material

The main components of input material were found to be proteins and fats. The amount of fixed carbon is very low in all samples. Elemental analysis showed the highest amount of C, followed by H and N. As for other elements, Ca and P were the most abundant. The thermogravimetric curves show that the highest weight loss was achieved with samples from pork bones.

3.2. Pyrolysis product yields

The solid, liquid, and gas phase yields obtained by pyrolysis show that the various pyrolysis conditions are not as decisive as the type of input material itself. The highest solid yield was achieved with samples from beef bones.

3.3. Characterization of solid phase

The amounts of volatiles in the samples are within a narrow range, and the amount of ash generally increases at the expense of fixed carbon. Elemental and Raman analyses revealed the carbon content. XRF analysis shows the amount of Ca and P, while XRD and FTIR analyses revealed the presence of hydroxyapatite. Nitrogen physisorption isotherms confirm the presence of macropores and mesopores.

3.4. VOC adsorption capacity

According to adsorption capacities, the samples can be sorted in descending order as follows: beef >pork >chicken.

4. Conclusion

This study focuses on the preparation of char as a VOC adsorbent. The type of input material had a greater impact on pyrolytic yield than the pyrolysis conditions. The pyrolytic yields of the different types of input material can be summarised as follows: the highest yields in the solid, liquid and gas phases were found for samples from beef and chicken bones, respectively. Samples exhibit meso–macroporous

structure. Samples prepared from beef and pork bones showed the highest VOC adsorption capacity, while those prepared from pork bones showed the highest specific surface area. The results gathered in this study lay the groundwork for future research into the production of chars for VOC abatement.

Declarations

Funding:

The financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH - Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries project No. CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition is gratefully acknowledged. The research was also funded by the MATUR – Materials and Technologies for Sustainable Development project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 and the work was also supported by the OP JAK project "INOVO!!!", No. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_021/0008588 supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports and co-financed by the European Union. Experimental results were accomplished by using Large Research Infrastructure ENREGAT supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic under projects no. LM2018098 and LM2023056.

Data availability:

Open research data will be available on Zenodo in the final version of the manuscript.

References

1. Cascarosa E, Gea G, Arauzo J (2012) Thermochemical processing of meat and bone meal: A review. *Renew Sustainable Energy Reviews* 16(1):942–957
2. Cortes LN et al (2019) Preparation of carbonaceous materials from pyrolysis of chicken bones and its application for fuchsine adsorption. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 26(28):28574–28583
3. Yang YX et al (2020) Surface modified and activated waste bone char for rapid and efficient VOCs adsorption. *Chemosphere* 256:9
4. Du WY et al (2017) Biomass-derived nitrogen-doped hierarchically porous carbon networks as efficient absorbents for phenol removal from wastewater over a wide pH range. *RSC Adv* 7(74):46629–46635
5. Medellin-Castillo NA et al (2007) Adsorption of fluoride from water solution on bone char. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 46(26):9205–9212
6. Rojas-Mayorga CK et al (2013) Optimization of pyrolysis conditions and adsorption properties of bone char for fluoride removal from water. *J Anal Appl Pyrol* 104:10–18
7. Alkurdi SSA et al (2020) Effect of pyrolysis conditions on bone char characterization and its ability for arsenic and fluoride removal. *Environ Pollut*, 262

8. Shahid MK et al (2020) Effect of pyrolysis conditions on characteristics and fluoride adsorptive performance of bone char derived from bone residue. *J Water Process Eng*, 37
9. Cascarosa E et al (2012) Sulphur removal using char and ash from meat and bone meal pyrolysis. *Biomass Bioenergy* 40:190–193
10. Piccirillo C (2023) Preparation, characterisation and applications of bone char, a food waste-derived sustainable material: A review. *J Environ Manage*, 339
11. Azeem M et al (2021) Bone-derived biochar improved soil quality and reduced Cd and Zn phytoavailability in a multi-metal contaminated mining soil. *Environ Pollut*, 277
12. Tala W et al (2016) Development of low-cost passive sampler from cow bone char for sampling of volatile organic compounds. *Int J Environ Sci Technol* 13(7):1685–1696
13. Vastyl M et al (2022) A case study on microwave pyrolysis of waste tyres and cocoa pod husk; effect on quantity and quality of utilizable products. *J Environ Chem Eng*, 10(1)
14. Jankovská Z et al (2024) Microporous carbon prepared by microwave pyrolysis of scrap tyres and the effect of K + in its structure on xylene adsorption. *Carbon* 216:118581

Figures

Figure 1

VOC adsorption capacities (square pattern) and specific surface areas (dotted pattern) of samples from beef, pork and chicken bones.